

A STUDY OF PROPERTIES AND REAL-LIFE APPLICATIONS OF NEGATIVE BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION

¹Mansi Verma, ²Ravinder Kaur, ³Savneet Kaur

¹Research Scholar, Dept. of Mathematics, Desh Bhagat University, Mandi Gobindgarh, Punjab, India

²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Mathematics, Desh Bhagat University, Mandi Gobindgarh, Punjab, India

³Assistant Professor, Dept. of Chemistry, Desh Bhagat University, Mandi Gobindgarh, Punjab, India

ABSTRACT

This paper delves deep into the characteristics and practical uses of the Negative Binomial Distribution, a discrete probability model extensively utilized across multiple domains such as epidemiology, insurance, and ecology. The exploration commences with a detailed examination of the mathematical attributes of the Negative Binomial Distribution, encompassing its probability mass function, moments, and methodologies for parameter estimation. By conducting this thorough investigation, the objective is to emphasize the importance of the Negative Binomial Distribution in both theoretical and practical scenarios, serving as a valuable reference for scholars and professionals confronted with excessively dispersed count data in diverse fields. This in-depth analysis seeks to shed light on the critical role played by the Negative Binomial Distribution in statistical modeling and empirical studies, offering insights and tools for analyzing data sets characterized by over-dispersion, thus enhancing the understanding and application of this powerful probability distribution.

I INTRODUCTION

The Negative Binomial Distribution is a captivating and crucial component of probability theory and statistics, renowned for its distinctive features and practical applications in diverse domains, including biology, finance, and engineering. At its fundamental core, this distribution models the number of trials necessary to obtain a specified quantity of successes in a succession of independent and identically distributed Bernoulli trials. This renders it particularly advantageous for scenarios where events occur randomly, and there is an interest in comprehending the variability in the number of attempts required to achieve a certain number of successes[5]. The Negative Binomial Distribution is a flexible and versatile probability distribution that can be used to model a wide range of real-world phenomena, such as the number of failures before a certain number of successes are observed in a series of independent Bernoulli trials, the number of attempts required to achieve a desired number of positive outcomes, or the number of customers entering a store until a specific number of sales are made. Its ability to capture the uncertainty and variability inherent in these types of situations has made it a valuable tool in fields like epidemiology, reliability engineering, and quality control, where understanding the underlying patterns and probabilities is crucial for effective decision-making and problem-solving. The Negative Binomial Distribution's connection to the geometric distribution, where the number of required successes is limited to one, is a captivating aspect of this statistical model. By expanding upon this foundation, the Negative Binomial Distribution offers a more versatile framework for analyzing scenarios that involve multiple successes. This extension enables a more comprehensive and sophisticated understanding of stochastic processes and random variable behavior. The Negative Binomial Distribution generalizes the geometric distribution by allowing for the specification of the number of required successes, rather than just one. This added flexibility allows for the modeling of a wider range of real-world phenomena, such as 2 the number of trials required to obtain a certain number of successes in a series of independent Bernoulli trials. The Negative Binomial Distribution's ability to capture more complex data patterns makes it a valuable tool in fields like reliability engineering, epidemiology, and finance, where the occurrence of multiple successes is of interest. The Negative Binomial Distribution is a commonly used statistical model in practical applications where the occurrence of events follows a pattern of repeated trials with varying outcomes. Thus, The Negative Binomial Distribution is a sophisticated and flexible statistical instrument that augments our capacity to model and comprehend intricate stochastic phenomena. Its robust theoretical underpinnings, coupled with practical utility across a wide range of domains, render it a crucial component in the statistician's repertoire. This distribution provides a resilient framework for addressing

uncertainty and variability when forecasting disease propagation, optimizing marketing approaches, or analyzing count data, thereby enhancing our understanding about the real world.

II NEGATIVE BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION

The Negative Binomial distribution is a discrete probability distribution utilized to represent the number of trials required to achieve a predetermined number of successes in a sequence of independent and identically distributed Bernoulli trials. This distribution serves as a generalization of the geometric distribution, which specifically focuses on the number of trials essential to attain the initial success in a series of independent trials that either result in success or failure based on a constant probability. Negative Binomial distribution thus provides a broader scope by accounting for multiple successes within the specified number of trials, offering a comprehensive framework for statistical analysis and probability calculations.

DEFINITION

The Negative Binomial distribution, a probability distribution used in statistics and probability theory, can be defined in two common ways, depending on whether the total number of trials includes or excludes the specified fixed number of successes. This versatile distribution is valuable for modeling the number of failures before obtaining a predetermined number of successes in sequential trials.

• Number of Failures Before r-th Success:

If X is the random variable representing the number of failures before the r -th success, then X follows a Negative Binomial distribution with parameters r (number of successes) and p (probability of success in each trial).

The Negative Binomial distribution (PMF) is given by:

$$P(X = k) = \binom{k+r-1}{r-1} p^r (1-p)^k$$

Where k is the number of failures (non-negative integer). $k = \binom{k+r-1}{r-1} (1-p)^k p^r$

• Total Number of Trials to achieve r-th Success:

If Y is the random variable representing the total number of trials to achieve the r -th success, then Y follows a Negative Binomial distribution with parameters r and p .

The Negative Binomial distribution (PMF) is given by:

$$P(Y = n) = \binom{n-1}{r-1} p^r (1-p)^{n-r}$$

Where, n is the total number of trials and $n \geq r$.

If X is the random variable representing the number of failures before the r -th success, then X follows a Negative Binomial

III PARAMETERS AND PROPERTIES OF NEGATIVE BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION

A PARAMETERS OF NEGATIVE BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION

(a) Number of Successes (r):

- The target number of successful outcomes.
- Must be a positive integer.

(b) Probability of Success (p):

- The probability of a success on an individual trial.
- $0 < p \leq 1$.

(c) Probability of Failure (q):

- The probability of a failure on an individual trial.
- $q = 1 - p$.

B PROPERTIES OF NEGATIVE BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION

(a) Mean

In a negative binomial distribution with parameters (r, p) , the expected total number of failures can be derived as $r(1-p)/p$.

To better understand this concept, consider an experiment where the negative binomial scenario is replicated numerous times. This involves conducting sets of trials until achieving r successes, then repeating the process multiple times, each time obtaining new sets of trials. Denote the trials in each experiment as a , b , c , and so on, summing them up to N . Consequently, an anticipated outcome would be around Np successes in total across these experiments. Let's say the experiment is repeated n times, resulting in a total of nr successes altogether. Hence, we can infer that $nr = Np$, leading to the relationship $N/n = r/p$. Here, N/n signifies the average number of trials in each experiment, thus representing the concept of "expectation." Furthermore, the average number of failures per experiment can be calculated as $N/n - r$, simplifying to $r/p - r$, which equals $r(1 - p)/p$. This calculation corresponds with the mean value presented in the box on the right side of this page, reinforcing the understanding of the expected number of failures in a negative binomial distribution based on the given parameters.

$$E[X] = \frac{r(1-p)}{p}$$

This represents the expected number of failures before achieving r successes.

(b) Variance

When determining the variance of events like the number of failures before the r -th success, an insightful formula emerges, which showcases how statistical measures can shed light on various scenarios. This variance, denoted by $r(1 - p)/p^2$, illuminates the interplay between failure occurrences and the ultimate success, offering a glimpse into the dynamics of such processes. Similarly, when considering the count of successes prior to the r -th failure – a nuanced perspective captured in an alternative formulation as presented in (3) – the variance equation of $rp/(1 - p)^2$ unravels a different facet of probability analysis. These mathematical expressions not only provide numerical insights but also underscore the intricate relationships between successes, failures, and the convergence towards specific milestones within a given sequence of events. Examining these variance calculations from multiple angles enriches our understanding of the underlying probabilities, lending depth to the statistical analysis and reinforcing the significance of interpreting results within a broader framework of probabilistic reasoning. In essence, the variance metrics serve as informative tools that offer a structured approach to quantifying uncertainties and exploring the patterns inherent in success-failure sequences, thereby contributing to a comprehensive analysis of probabilistic phenomena in diverse contexts.

$$Var(X) = \frac{r(1-p)}{p^2}$$

This represents the variability in the number of failures before achieving r successes.

(c) Moment-Generating Function

The Negative Binomial distribution is a probability distribution used to model the number of successes before a specified number of failures occur. For this distribution, the moment-generating function (MGF) provides a convenient way to calculate various moments of the distribution. The MGF of the Negative Binomial distribution is an important tool in probability theory and statistics, enabling the calculation of moments such as the mean, variance, and higher order moments. It allows for the simplification of complex calculations and provides a unified approach to understanding the distribution's properties. The moment-generating function (MGF) of the Negative Binomial distribution is given by:

$$M_X(t) = \left(\frac{pe^t}{1 - (1-p)e^t} \right)^r, \text{ for } t < -\ln(1-p)$$

(d) Probability Generating Function

The Negative Binomial distribution is a probability model frequently used in statistics to describe the number of trials needed to achieve a certain number of successes. By evaluating the PGF, one can gain insights into the behavior of the Negative Binomial distribution in terms of its mean, variance, and higher moments. Overall, understanding the PGF of the Negative Binomial distribution enhances our ability to interpret data and draw meaningful conclusions from statistical analyses. The probability generating function (PGF) of the Negative Binomial distribution is given by:

$$G_X(s) = \left(\frac{ps}{1 - (1-p)s} \right)^r, \text{ for } |s| < \frac{1}{1-p}$$

(e) Cumulative Distribution Function

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) is a statistical concept that characterizes the probability distribution of a random variable. It provides valuable insights into how the probability of a certain outcome accumulates as values increase. The cumulative distribution function (CDF) is more complex but can be expressed using the regularized incomplete beta function

Ix (a,b) :

$$F(k; r, p) = 1 - I_p(k + 1, r), \text{ for } k \geq 0$$

(f) Skewness:

Skewness is a statistical measure that helps describe the asymmetry of probability distributions such as the negative binomial. In the case of negative binomial distributions, skewness serves as a crucial indicator of the shape of the distribution. Specifically, a negative binomial distribution with high skewness suggests a significant departure from symmetry, implying that one tail of the distribution is longer than the other.

Skewness indicates the asymmetry of the probability distribution. If p is small, the skewness is large, indicating a long tail on the right.

$$\text{Skewness} = \frac{2 - p}{\sqrt{r(1 - p)}}$$

(g) Kurtosis:

Kurtosis is a statistical measure that provides insights into the shape of a distribution by indicating how much of the distribution is concentrated in the tails. Essentially, higher kurtosis signifies that the distribution has more weight in the tails compared to a normal distribution, making it an important metric for understanding the distribution's overall behavior. Ultimately, by interpreting kurtosis values, researchers and analysts can gain a deeper understanding of the distribution's characteristics and make informed decisions based on the distribution's "tailedness" and the presence of potentially influential outliers.

Kurtosis measures the "tailedness" of the distribution. Higher values indicate a distribution with heavier tails.

$$\text{Kurtosis} = \frac{6}{r} + \frac{(1 - p)^2}{rp}$$

IV VERIFICATION OF REAL-LIFE APPLICATIONS OF NEGATIVE BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION

Problem: Probability of hitting a six on any given ball is 0.05. Find the distribution of the number of balls a player faces before hitting 4 sixes in a cricket match (Using NBD).

Solution: Given:

$r=4$ (we want 4 successes)

$p=0.05$ (probability of success on each six)

The probability mass function (PMF) of the Negative Binomial distribution is given by:

$$P(Y = n) = \binom{n-1}{r-1} p^r (1-p)^{n-r}$$

Now, calculating the probabilities for different values of k : For, $k=6$ (6 Balls)

$$P(Y=6) = \binom{6-1}{4-1} (1-0.05)^{6-4} \cdot 0.05^4$$

$$= \binom{5}{3} \cdot 0.95^2 \cdot 0.05^4$$

$$= 10 \times 6.25 \times 10^{-7} \times 0.9025$$

$$= 5.64 \times 10^{-6}$$

Similarly,

$$P(X=8) = 0.0000178$$

$$P(X=7) = 0.0000107$$

$$P(X=12) = 0.0000683$$

$$P(X=14) = 0.000107$$

No. of Balls	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5
1.	6 Runs	6 Runs	6 Runs	4 Runs	Runs
2.	6 Runs	0 Runs	0 Run	6 Runs	4 Runs
3.	0 Runs	6 Runs	6 Runs	3 Runs	2 Runs
4.	4 Runs	2 Runs	4 Runs	2 Runs	0 Run
5.	6 Runs	6 Runs	6 Runs	6 Runs	6 Runs
6.	6 Runs	1 Run	1 Run	0 Run	0 Run
7.		4 Runs	6 Runs	1 Run	0 Run
8.		6 Runs		4 Runs	6 Runs
9.				2 Runs	2 Runs
10.				6 Runs	1 Run
11.				0 Run	4 Runs
12.				6 Runs	6 Runs
13.					3 Runs
14.					6 Runs

V CONCLUSION

Its versatility extends across various fields, making it indispensable for researchers and practitioners engaged in probabilistic modeling and statistical analysis. It enriches the learner's understanding of the Negative Binomial Probability Distribution and its relevance in everyday situations. The Negative Binomial Distribution is not merely a mathematical formula but a tool whose outcomes hold true applicability in real-world scenarios, particularly in cases where there is a need to model the number of trials required to achieve a set number of successes or failures in discrete, independent events.

REFERENCES

1. The Mathematical Papers of Isaac Newton," edited by D.T. Whiteside.Abraham deMoivre's "The
2. Doctrine of Chances" (1718)
3. "Generalized Linear Models" by P. McCullagh and J.A. Nelder (1989)
4. "The Probable Error of a Mean" by William Sealy Gosset (1876-1937
5. "Continuous Univariate Distributions" (Volumes 1 and 2) by Norman L. Johnson, Samuel Kotz, and N. Balakrishnan
6. "The Normal Distribution: Characterizations with Applications" by N. Balakrishnan
7. Jacques Bernoulli (1654-1705): A Collection of Historical Essays
8. Statistical Inference: A Short Course" by David J. Olive
9. International Refereed Journal of Engineering and Science (IRJES) ISSN (Online)2319-183X, (Print) 2319-1821 Volume 2, Issue 6(June 2013), PP.33-43
10. https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-0-387-32833-1_277